

Study of Saponins from *Albizzia lebbek* Benth Flowers

I. P. VARSHNEY and D. C. JAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Garhwal, Srinagar-Garhwal-246 174
and

H. C. SRIVASTAVA

Chemistry Division, Ahmedabad Textile Industry's Research Association, Ahmedabad-380 015

Manuscript received 27 January 1981, accepted 24 March 1982

Albizzia lebbek Benth flowers yield a number of saponins named as lebbekaniin-D, F, G and H. They are all glycosides of echinocystic acid with varying sugars. On the basis of enzymatic, partial alkaline hydrolysis, methylation and periodate oxidation studies, partial structures have been assigned to these saponins.

ALBIZZIA lebbek Benth commonly known as *Siris* belongs to the family Leguminosae. Varshney *et al*¹⁻⁸ have studied various parts of this tree and isolated eight new saponins named as lebbekaniin A, B, C, D, E, F, G and H. The present paper describes the study of lebbekaniin D, F, G and H, isolated from the flowers of this plant.

Air dried flowers, after defatting with light petroleum ether, were exhaustively extracted with ethanol. The ethanol extract on concentration and usual treatment¹ yielded a light brown substance which gave all the tests for triterpenic saponins.

The crude saponin was then separated into 4 pure saponins, lebbekaniin D, F, G and H by repeated column chromatography on silica gel, lebbekaniin D being the major part of the mixture.

Study of lebbekaniin D: Lebbekaniin D, m.p. 217-18°, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -27.5°, (MeOH, c, 1%), R_f 0.350 (chloroform : methanol : water 65 : 40 : 10), on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid gave echinocystic acid (3 β ,16 α -dihydroxy olean-12-ene-28 oic acid) (20.1%), and a mixture of five sugars, glucose, galactose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose in the molar ratio 2 : 2 : 5 : 3 : 3.

Lebbekaniin D on alkaline hydrolysis with 5% methanolic potassium hydroxide solution gave a prosapogenin-D₁ and an oligosaccharide-D₁ indicating the presence of ester linkage in the lebbekaniin D (i.e. attachment of sugars at C-28 COOH group also). The attachment of sugars at C-16 OH group is not possible due to its strongly hindered position showing thereby that all the sugars are attached at C-3 OH and C-28 COOH groups. The oligosaccharide-D₁ on complete hydrolysis gave glucose, galactose and rhamnose in the molar ratio 1 : 1 : 3. The prosapogenin-D₁ on complete hydrolysis with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid gave four sugars, glucose, galactose, arabinose and xylose in the molar ratio 1 : 1 : 5 : 3 and echinocystic acid as genin.

Lebbekaniin-D on mild alkaline hydrolysis with 2% methanolic KOH gave prosapogenin-D₂ and oligosaccharide-D₂. Prosapogenin-D₂ on complete hydrolysis with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid gave same four sugars glucose, galactose, arabinose and xylose and a neutral genin, m.p. 210-13°, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +36.9° (EtOH, c, 1%), R_f 0.726, in place of echinocystic acid, m.p. 308-8°, R_f 0.414 (benzene : acetone 6 : 1) isolated by the hydrolysis of prosapogenin D₁. Oligosaccharide D₂ on complete hydrolysis gave the same three sugars i.e., glucose, galactose and rhamnose.

The neutral genin thus obtained (m.p. 210-13°) gave positive tests for triterpenic sapogenins and a double bond. The spectral studies $[\text{IR}_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}} : \nu 1700-1720 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ (s) (COOCH}_3\text{)}; \text{nmr (CDCl}_3\text{)} : \delta 3.8 \text{ (s) (3H; COOCH}_3\text{)}, 5.5 \text{ (s) (1H; olifinic)}, 4.6 \text{ (s) (2H; OH)}]$ showed it to be methyl ester of echinocystic acid. The above spectral data tally with the reported data⁹ of methyl ester of echinocystic acid. The identity was also confirmed by co-tlc and m.m.p. with an authentic sample of the ester.

This led to the conclusion that glucose, galactose and rhamnose (1 : 1 : 3) are attached to C-28 COOH group as ester and when lebbekaniin D is reacted with 2% methanolic KOH the sugars from the C-28 COOH group are knocked out and methyl group from methanol gets attached to COOH at C-28, giving methyl ester of echinocystic acid as neutral genin.

One strange thing is noted. When hydrolysis of lebbekaniin-D is carried out with 5% methanolic KOH no methylation takes place at C-28 COOH group or if it takes place, the methyl group is knocked out by the strong concentration of KOH in alkaline hydrolysis and a potassium salt of echinocystic acid is formed. The 2% methanolic KOH, on the contrary, is not sufficient to remove the methyl group and formation of potassium salt of echinocystic acid is not possible (Fig. 1)

Prosapogenin- D_1 and oligosaccharide D_1 , obtained on 5% methanolic KOH hydrolysis were separated and their methylation, partial hydrolysis, enzymatic hydrolysis, periodate oxidation were carried out.

Study of prosapogenin- D_1 : Prosapogenin- D_1 , m.p. 205-8°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -24.3^\circ$ (meOH c, 1%), R_f 0.46 (chloroform, methanol : water 65 : 40 : 10), on acid hydrolysis with 2N aqueous sulphuric acid gave echinocystic acid and a mixture of four sugars, glucose, galactose, arabinose and xylose in molar ratio 1 : 1 : 5 : 3.

In order to find out the attachment and sequence of the sugars, prosapogenin- D_1 was methylated by Hakomori's method¹⁰ followed by two Purdie methylation¹¹ in order to ensure complete methylation (checked by ir spectra). Fully methylated prosapogenin was subjected to methanolysis with 3% methanolic hydrogen chloride. The resulting methylglycoside of methylated sugars obtained were identified by glc on 8% OS-138 on chromosorb W column (NAW), relative retention times were determined taking methyl 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl- α -D-glucosides as reference. Following methylglycosides of methylated sugars were tentatively identified :

- (i) Methyl-2,3,4-tri-O-methyl- β -D-xyloside.
- (ii) Methyl-2,3,5-tri-O-methyl- α -L-arabinoside.
- (iii) Methyl-3,4-di-O-methyl- β -D xyloside.
- (iv) Methyl-2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl- α -D-glucoside.
- (v) Methyl-3-O-methyl- α -L-arabinoside.
- (vi) Methyl-2-O-methyl- α -L-arabinoside.
- (vii) Methyl-2,3,6-tri-O-methyl- α -D-galactoside.

Prosapogenin- D_1 on partial hydrolysis with 0.1N aqueous sulphuric acid on water bath for 1 hr gave three sugars, glucose arabinose and xylose but galactose was not liberated. This showed the back bone position of galactose. On partial hydrolysis for 1 hr three sugars, glucose, arabinose and xylose

were liberated. This indicates that these sugars were linked through weak linkages or had a terminal position in the sugar chain. Presence of methyl ethers of arabinose in methyl sugars shows that the branching is taking place through these molecule.

Prosapogenin- D_1 was treated with NaIO_4 (0.5M), oxidised prosapogenin was extracted with *n*-butanol and was hydrolysed. The hydrolysate showed the presence of only arabinose. It confirms that branching is taking place through arabinose and also support the methylation results.

Study of oligosaccharide D_1 : Oligosaccharide D_1 was completely methylated by Hakomori's method followed by one Purdie methylation. Complete methylation was checked by ir spectra. Methylated oligosaccharide was subjected to methanolysis in the usual manner. The methyl glycosides of methylated sugars obtained were identified by glc under similar conditions. Following methylglycosides of different methyl sugars were identified :

- (i) Methyl-2,3,4-tri-O-methyl- α -L-rhamnoside.
- (ii) Methyl-3,4-di-O-methyl- α -L-rhamnoside.
- (iii) Methyl-2,3,6-tri-O-methyl- α -D-glucoside.
- (iv) Methyl-2,3-di-O-methyl- α -D-galactoside.

Methylation results showed that the two rhamnose molecules have terminal positions whereas glucose, galactose and one rhamnose are present in the back bone position. Branching is taking place through galactose molecule as it comes as 2,3-di-O-methyl- α -D-galactose.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of lebbekinin-D with β -glucosidase did not liberate any sugar indicating the absence of β -glycosidic linkage in the glucose molecule.

Since the attachment of sugars at C-16 OH group is not possible due to its strongly hindered position, the only possibility that remains is of C-3 OH group

which is the usual position for the attachment of sugars in the case of triterpenic saponins. Thus, lebbekinin-D has two sugar chains, one attached to the C-28 COOH group and other at the C-3 OH group.

On the basis of above results partial structure of lebbekinin-D may be assigned as structure (I).

Study of lebbekinin-F: Lebbekinin F, m.p. 204-5°, $[\alpha]_D -40^\circ$ (MeOH c, 1%), R_f 0.453, on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* aqueous sulphuric acid gave an acid genin (24.5%). It has been identified as echinocystic acid by direct comparison.

The hydrolysate obtained was neutralized and deionised and on paper chromatography showed the presence of five sugars identified as glucose, arabinose, xylose, fucose and rhamnose present in the molar ratio 2 : 2 : 2 : 1 : 3.

Lebbekinin-F on alkaline hydrolysis with 5% methanolic/KOH on boiling water bath gave prosapogenin-F and oligosaccharide-F, indicating the presence of ester linkage in saponin i.e. attachment of sugars at C-28 COOH group.

Oligosaccharide-F on complete hydrolysis gave three sugars identified as glucose, xylose and rhamnose. Prosapogenin-F on complete hydrolysis gave five sugars glucose, arabinose, xylose, fucose and rhamnose.

Lebbekinin-F on partial hydrolysis with 0.1*N* sulphuric acid for 1 hr gave four sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose only. On enzymatic hydrolysis with β -glucosidase, it did not liberate any sugar indicating the absence of β -linkage.

Since the attachment of sugar at C-16 OH groups is not possible due to its strongly hindered position, all the sugars are attached at C-3 OH and C-28 COOH groups.

On the basis of above results lebbekinin-F has been assigned structure (II).

Fig. 2

- (I) $R + R' = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{rha}.$ (2 : 2 : 5 : 3 : 3)
 $R = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl}$ (1 : 1 : 5 : 3)
 $R' = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{rha}$ (1 : 1 : 3)
- (II) $R + R' = \text{Glu} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{fuc} : \text{rha}.$ (2 : 2 : 2 : 1 : 3)
 $R = \text{Glu} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{fuc} : \text{rha}$
 $R' = \text{Glu} : \text{xyl} : \text{rha}.$
- (III) $R + R' = \text{Glu} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{fuc} : \text{rha}.$ (3 : 2 : 2 : 2 : 3)
 $R = \text{Glu} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{fuc} : \text{rha}$
 $R' = \text{Glu} : \text{xyl} : \text{rha}.$
- (IV) $R + R' = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl} : \text{rha}.$ (4 : 2 : 3 : 3 : 3)
 $R = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{ara} : \text{xyl}$
 $R' = \text{Glu} : \text{gal} : \text{rha}.$

Study of lebbekinin-G: Lebbekinin-G, m.p. 210-12°, $[\alpha]_D -38.5^\circ$ (MeOH c, 1%), R_f 0.390, on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* H_2SO_4 gave an acid genin (18%) which was identified as echinocystic acid and five sugars glucose, arabinose, xylose, fucose and rhamnose present in the molar ratio 3 : 2 : 2 : 2 : 3.

Lebbekinin-G on alkaline hydrolysis with 5% methanolic KOH gave prosapogenin-G and oligosaccharide-G indicating the presence of ester linkage i.e. attachment of sugars at C-28 COOH group.

Oligosaccharide-G on complete hydrolysis gave three sugars glucose, xylose and rhamnose. Prosapogenin-G on complete hydrolysis gave five sugars, glucose, arabinose, xylose, fucose and rhamnose.

Lebbekinin-G on partial hydrolysis with 0.1*N* H_2SO_4 gave glucose and rhamnose after 1 hr and glucose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose after 2 hr while on enzymatic hydrolysis with β -glucosidase, did not liberate any sugar indicating the absence of β -linkage.

On the basis of above results lebbekinin-G has been assigned the structure (III).

Study of lebbekinin H: Lebbekinin-H, m.p. 220-22°, $[\alpha]_D -27.13^\circ$ (MeOH c, 1%), R_f 0.324, on acid hydrolysis with 2*N* H_2SO_4 gave an acid genin (15.5%) identified as echinocystic acid and five sugars glucose, galactose, arabinose, xylose and rhamnose, present in the molar ratio 4 : 2 : 3 : 3 : 3.

Lebbekinin-H on alkaline hydrolysis with 5% methanolic KOH gave prosapogenin-H and oligosaccharide-H showing the presence of ester linkage in saponin i.e. attachment of sugars at C-28 COOH group.

Prosapogenin-H on complete hydrolysis gave four sugars glucose, galactose, arabinose and xylose while oligosaccharide-G gave three sugars glucose, galactose and rhamnose

Lebbekinin-H on partial hydrolysis with 0.1*N* H_2SO_4 gave glucose and rhamnose after 1 hr. On enzymatic hydrolysis with β -glucosidase no sugar was liberated showing the absence of β -linkage.

On the basis of above results lebbekinin-H has been assigned the structure (IV).

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (D. C. J.).

References

1. I. P. VARSHNEY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 446.
2. I. P. VARSHNEY, G. BADHWAR, H. C. SRIVASTAVA and T. N. KRISHNAMURTHY, *Planta Medica*, 1973, 24, 183.

VARSHNEY, JAIN & SRIVASTAVA : STUDY OF SAPONINS FROM *Albizzia Lebbek* BENTH FLOWERS

3. I. P. VARSHNEY, G. HANDA (NEE BADHWAR), H. C. SRIVASTAVA and T. N. KRISHNAMURTHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 1094.
4. I. P. VARSHNEY and G. HANDA, (unpublished), Ph.D. thesis of Geeta Handa, University of Indore, 1971.
5. I. P. VARSHNEY, G. BADHWAR and RAJPAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1202.
6. I. P. VARSHNEY and M. S. Y. KHAN, *Cand. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1721.
7. I. P. VARSHNEY, RAJPAL and P. VYAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **55**, 859.
8. I. P. VARSHNEY and D. C. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16B**, 1131.
9. G. K. JAIN, J. P. S. SARIN and N. M. KHANNA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15B**, 1139.
10. S. HAKOMORI, *J. Biochem. (Tokyo)*, 1964, **55**, 205.
11. T. PURDIE and J. C. IRVINE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 1021.